

THE IMPORTANCE OF DEVELOPING HEARING PERCEPTION AND TEACHING PRONUNCIATION IN THE ADAPTATION OF CHILDREN WITH HEARING IMPAIRMENTS TO LIFE

Xonbabayeva Madinabonu Asqarjon qizi

Kokand State Pedagogical Institute, Teacher of the Department of Special Pedagogy.

Abdumalikova Nazokatxon Akmaljon qizi

Teacher at Specialized Educational Institution No. 1 in Fergana City, which is designed for children with special educational needs, including those who are deaf or hard of hearing.

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Abstract: This article highlights the significance of activities aimed at developing hearing perception and pronunciation for children with hearing impairments (CHIs). The topic is relevant as it plays a crucial role in the social adaptation, self-awareness, and communication skills of CHIs. The article analyzes the role of hearing perception in the social and personal development of children, the relationship between pronunciation and hearing perception, as well as the opportunities for speech development and communication skills enhancement through the formation of language perception.

Keywords: hearing perception, pronunciation development, social adaptation, communication skills, self-awareness, language perception formation, phonemic hearing, independence, social integration, speech development, self-confidence, special exercises, teaching methods, cognitive development.

Children with hearing impairments (CHIs) face difficulties in finding their place in life, integrating into society, and expressing themselves. Activities for developing hearing perception and pronunciation play a very important role in their development. CHIs often encounter problems in establishing social connections, expressing their thoughts freely, and participating in the educational process. This, in turn, can negatively impact their psychological and emotional development.

Activities for developing hearing perception and teaching pronunciation are essential for shaping children's language and speech skills, as well as strengthening their social adaptation. Hearing perception exercises help children accurately analyze and understand surrounding sounds, as well as participate in the communication process. Pronunciation development enables children to express their thoughts clearly and understandably.

The main objectives of the activities are as follows:

1. **Developing Hearing Perception:** Improving the hearing abilities of CHIs, as well as shaping skills to distinguish between sounds and phonemes. This is crucial for developing children's ability to understand and differentiate sounds.
2. **Teaching Pronunciation:** Pronunciation exercises help ensure that children's speech is clear and accurate. This, in turn, lays the foundation for their success in social relationships.
3. **Supporting Social Adaptation:** Through hearing perception and pronunciation skills, children will be able to actively participate in communication, establish friendships, and move freely within social environments.
4. **Self-Awareness and Self-Expression:** CHIs will have the opportunity to express their thoughts and feelings clearly, understand their abilities, and develop self-confidence.

Hearing perception and pronunciation play a vital role in children's social and personal development. The success of CHIs in life largely depends on their hearing abilities and speech skills. This section highlights the impact of hearing perception on children's development, the connection between hearing and pronunciation, and the development of speech and communication skills through language perception formation.

1. The Role of Hearing Perception in the Social and Personal Development of Children

Hearing perception is an essential part of understanding the surrounding environment and social interactions for children. Through sounds and noises, children communicate with friends, family members, and teachers. The development of hearing perception also includes the following factors:

- **Social Connections:** CHIs may face difficulties in communication compared to children with developed hearing abilities. By developing hearing perception, children learn to communicate effectively with others, which strengthens their social connections.
- **Personal Development:** By accurately analyzing and understanding sounds, children learn to express their emotions. This process helps enhance their self-awareness and self-confidence.
- **Educational Process:** Hearing perception allows children to actively participate in the educational process. Through sounds and conversations, children can comprehend educational materials and feel comfortable in the educational environment.

2. The Relationship Between the Development of Hearing Perception and Pronunciation

Hearing and pronunciation are closely interconnected. Through hearing perception, children develop the ability to accurately distinguish and recognize sounds and phonemes. This process aids in the proper formation of pronunciation.

- **Phonemic Hearing:** Children learn to differentiate and distinguish sounds, which is crucial for making speech clear and understandable. The development of phonemic hearing improves pronunciation and ensures the integrity of speech.
- **Challenges in Pronunciation:** Children with reduced hearing perception may encounter difficulties in developing pronunciation. Due to their lack of necessary skills to accurately pronounce sounds, it is essential to enhance their hearing abilities through specialized exercises.

3. Developing Speech and Communication Skills Through Language Perception Formation

Language perception is a crucial factor in the development of children's speech. To enhance auditory perception, shape language perception, and improve communication skills, the following aspects should be considered:

- **Language Structure:** Through auditory perception, children learn the structure of language, grammar, and vocabulary. This process enhances their communication abilities and enriches their speech.
- **Communication Skills:** By developing auditory perception and pronunciation, children improve their ability to express their thoughts, ask questions, and clarify their opinions. This facilitates their social adaptation.
- **Connection Between Hearing and Reading:** Improving auditory perception also enhances children's reading skills. By correctly distinguishing sounds and phonemes, children can succeed in the reading process.

The Importance and Methods of Activities

Special exercises and methods are essential for developing auditory perception and improving pronunciation. They serve to enhance children's hearing abilities, speech skills, and social integration. This section discusses effective methods for developing auditory perception, exercises for enhancing phonemic hearing, and pronunciation activities.

1. Special Exercises and Methods: Effective Ways to Develop Auditory Perception

There are several specialized exercises and methods for developing auditory perception. These mainly include:

- **Auditory Exercises:** Presenting children with various sounds to help them develop the ability to differentiate and recognize these sounds. These exercises assist children in enhancing their auditory abilities.
- **Sound Repetition:** Asking children to repeat different sounds to improve auditory perception. This exercise helps children understand sounds and adjust their pronunciation accordingly.
- **Social Situations:** Creating communication-focused scenarios where children can develop their auditory perception and speech skills. For example, using games, role-playing, and group activities.

2. Exercises for Developing Phonemic Hearing

The following exercises and techniques are used to develop phonemic hearing:

- **Imitation Exercises:** Asking children to imitate various sounds and phonemes. This method can be effective in developing their auditory perception.
- **Rhythm and Musical Exercises:** Introducing children to rhythmic and musical sounds. Through music, children can improve their auditory abilities as well as clarify their pronunciation.
- **Resonance Exercises:** Engaging children in exercises that focus on producing sounds and developing resonance. This method helps clarify their sounds and improve their pronunciation.

3. Pronunciation Exercises for Communication and Social Integration

To improve pronunciation and enhance social integration, the following exercises are employed:

- **Combining Sounds and Words:** Providing children with a specific set of words and teaching them to combine sounds and pronounce words. This exercise helps develop their speech abilities and social connections.
- **Role-Playing Games:** Children learn pronunciation through creating scenarios where they communicate with one another. This enhances social adaptation and strengthens their interpersonal relationships.
- **Simulating Social Situations:** By simulating various situations that arise during communication, children further develop their pronunciation and auditory perception.

The Importance of Activities in Social Adaptation

Activities focused on developing auditory perception and pronunciation play a crucial role in ensuring children's social adaptation. These activities not only enhance children's communicative skills but also improve their self-awareness and social integration. This section discusses the role of auditory perception and pronunciation activities in children's self-awareness, social adaptation, and communication skills, as well as the integration of children with special needs into life through the development of independence, self-confidence, and interests.

1. The Role of Auditory Perception and Pronunciation Activities in Children's Self-Awareness

Auditory perception and pronunciation activities help children develop self-awareness. They:

- **Express Their Emotions:** Children with special needs acquire the skills necessary to express themselves correctly. Through sounds and pronunciation, they convey their thoughts and feelings to society.
- **Understand Themselves:** Through auditory and pronunciation activities, children become aware of their abilities, strengths, and weaknesses. This enhances their self-confidence.
- **Develop Interpersonal Relationships:** Through communication, children establish connections with others and develop skills to participate in social interactions.

2. The Importance of Social Adaptation, Communication Skills, and Strengthening Integration with Society

Auditory perception and pronunciation activities play a crucial role in enhancing the social adaptation of children with special needs through several key avenues:

- **Developing Communication Skills:** Communication skills are vital for children with special needs. Engaging in various activities helps them learn to interact with peers, which is essential for their integration into society.
- **Adapting to the Social Environment:** These activities enable children to navigate social situations more effectively. They acquire skills that facilitate participation in interactions and help them understand social rules and norms.
- **Strengthening Social Integration:** As communication skills improve, children become better equipped to integrate into society. They gain valuable opportunities to engage in diverse social situations, form new friendships, and express themselves more freely.

3. Facilitating the Integration of Children with Special Needs into Life through the Development of Independence, Self-Confidence, and Interests

In addition, these activities assist children with special needs in cultivating independence, self-confidence, and interests:

- **Independence:** Through auditory perception and pronunciation exercises, children learn to showcase their abilities independently, fostering a sense of autonomy across various life domains.
- **Self-Confidence:** Participation in these activities boosts children's self-assurance. Improved auditory perception and pronunciation skills enhance their confidence, motivating them to engage actively in social settings.
- **Developing Interests:** Auditory perception and pronunciation activities can inspire children to explore new interests, contributing to their cognitive and social development.

Together, these elements significantly facilitate the integration of children with special needs into everyday life, empowering them to realize their full potential. Developing auditory perception and pronunciation is essential not only for personal growth but also for achieving successful integration into society.

References:

1. Tursunova, D. A. (2020). Pedagogik texnologiyalar yordamida talaffuzni yaxshilash. O'zbekiston ilm-fani va texnologiyalari, 2(1), 45-50.
2. Mirzaev, I. M. (2022). Zamonaviy ta'lim tizimida bolalarning eshitish qobiliyatini rivojlantirish. O'zbekiston ta'limi va innovatsiyalari, 8(1), 12-18.
3. Kolesnikov, P. P. (2015). Interactive Methods in Teaching Speech and Listening. Moscow: Publishing House of the Institute of Special Pedagogy.
4. Qizi, Xonbabayeva Madinabonu Asqarjon. "ESHITISHIDA NUQSONI BO'LGAN BOLALARNING RUHIY RIVOJLANISHI QONUNIYATLARI." Conferencea 12.12 (2023): 61-69.
5. Adxamovna, Ibragimova Dilfuza. "PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCE OF FUTURE LOGIC THERAPISTS IMPROVEMENT." Semiconductor Optoelectronics 42.2 (2023): 1457-1461.
6. QIZI, XONBABAYEVA MADINABONU ASQARJON. "STAGES OF DEVELOPMENT OF TEACHER PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCE." (2023).